

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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О журнале

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MORPHOFUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SMALL INTESTINE**Oripova N.A.**

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Resume. *The main functions of the small intestine are digestive - absorptive, immunological, endocrine and exocrine, evacuator and excretory functions. Due to the wide range of activities of the small intestine and possible adaptive changes, the study of its structure and functions is of particular interest to morphologists, immunologists and gastroenterologists. This article presents information on the development of the small intestine and its sections, the interaction of its layers, its vessels, the development of the innervation apparatus, its topography, histogenesis, and many other issues related to morpho-biochemical changes in this organ.*

Keywords: *small intestine, morphology, rat, postnatal ontogenesis, gastrointestinal tract.*

ИНГИЧКА ИЧАК РИВОЖЛАНИШИНИНГ МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ**Орипова Н.А.**

Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти, Бухоро ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. *Ингичка ичакнинг асосий функциялари овқат ҳазм қилиш – сўриш, иммунологик, эндова экзокрин, эвакуатор ва ажратиш функциялари ҳисобланади. Ингичка ичакнинг кенг спектрдаги фаолияти ва эҳтимоли бўлган мослашувчан ўзгаришлари туфайли унинг тузилиши ва функцияларини ўрганиш морфологлар, иммунологлар ва гастроэнтерологларнинг алоҳида қизиқишига сабаб ҳисобланади. Ушбу мақолада ингичка ичак ва унинг бўлимларининг ривожланиши, қатламларининг ўзаро таъсирлашуви, томирлари, иннервация аппаратининг ривожланиши, топографияси, гистогенези ва мазкур аъзода морфо-биокимёвий ўзгаришлар юзасидан бошқа кўплаб масалалар ҳақида маълумотлар келтирилган.*

Калим сўзлар: *ингичка ичак, морфология, каламуш, постнатал онтогенез, ошқозон-ичак тракти.*

МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ТОНКОЙ КИШКИ**Орипова Н.А.**

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Резюме. *Основными функциями тонкой кишки являются пищеварительно-всасывательная, иммунологическая, эндокринная и экзокринная, эвакуаторная и выделительная. В связи с широким спектром деятельности тонкой кишки и возможными адаптивными изменениями изучение ее строения и функций представляет особый интерес для морфологов, иммунологов и гастроэнтерологов. В статье представлены сведения о развитии тонкой кишки и её отделов, взаимодействии слоёв, сосудов, развитии иннервационного аппарата, топографии, гистогенезе и многих других вопросах, связанных с морфо-биохимическими изменениями в этом органе.*

Ключевые слова: *тонкая кишка, морфология, крыса, постнатальный онтогенез, желудочно-кишечный тракт.*

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Relevance Scientists believe that the small intestine is not only a part of the digestive system, but also an active component of the immune-endocrine system. Researchers have proven that many endocrine glands are activated in the small intestine. It has specific receptor areas, the activation of which affects the endocrine system. Therefore, the state of the small intestine is crucial for the hormonal processes of the whole organism [1]. The main functions of the small intestine are digestive - absorptive, immunological, endocrine and exocrine, evacuator and excretory functions. Due to the wide range of activities of the small intestine and its possible adaptive changes, the study of its structure and functions is of particular interest to morphologists, immunologists and gastroenterologists [2]. In the early postnatal period of the mammalian organism, the small intestine develops rapidly. In the first 7 days of life, the mass of the rat increases by an average of 2 times, and after 2 weeks - by 4 times. At the same time, the small intestine increases by 2 times, the diameter of the duodenum increases by 40%, the diameter of the small intestine by 40%, and the diameter of the

intestine between the ribs and the abdomen by 25%. The number of villi in the proximal and distal parts of the small intestine increases by 40 and 60%, respectively. Compared with the first days of life, a 2-fold increase in the number and depth of crypts is observed. With increasing age, crypts and villi are arranged in a more orderly manner, and their openings expand. All layers of the small intestine, especially the mucous membrane, thicken by the 14th day of life. The submucosal layer thickens, the muscular layer atrophies, making up about a third of the thickness of the intestinal wall [3].

On the 21st day of life, the functional and structural formation of the small intestine is completed. On the 15th day of postnatal ontogenesis, the structural components of the small intestine of the white rat (mucosa, its villi, crypts, epithelial cells, submucosal layer, muscular and serous layers) are formed. The thickness of the duodenal wall is 401.66 (11.80) μm , the thickness of the small intestine is 387.19 (7.91) μm , the thickness of the intestine between the ribs and the abdomen is 273.72 (16.56) μm ; height of hairs on mucosa, 207.40 (37.10) μm , 265.13 (3.19) μm , 121.35 (16.56) μm , respectively; crypt depth, 56.30 (2.10) μm , 50.41 (3.13) μm and 48.79 (8.90) μm , respectively. On the 45th day of postnatal development, the morphometric indicators of the studied structures in the white rat small intestine increase sharply. Hair height increases by 36.6% in the duodenum, 22.8% in the small intestine, and 44.9% in the rib and abdominal intestine [4].

The gastrointestinal tract is heavily colonized by a variety of microbes, including bacteria, fungi, viruses, and parasites. Bacteria are the most abundant, with up to 100 trillion microbial cells and more than 1000 species. Recently developed high-throughput sequencing technologies and data analysis methods have mapped the gut microbiome more precisely than traditional culture-based methods. This has allowed the study of specific species and even specific microbial structures. The composition and abundance of this microbial community is relatively homeostatic, depending on a variety of factors, such as dietary patterns, habitat, and host health. Dysbiosis, which includes compositional changes in the gut microbiota, may increase the risk of disease. The gut microbiota is increasingly recognized as an important environmental factor in the development of fibrogenesis [5].

To date, many studies have been conducted on the microbial influence of the gut on liver, heart, and nephritic fibrosis; in contrast, the influence of the gut on fibrosis has been studied only in part [6]. Unlike other organs of the gastrointestinal tract, it has a direct and intimate relationship with the intestinal microbiota; therefore, the microbial influences and mechanisms underlying intestinal fibrosis may be unique and require further study.

The gastrointestinal tract is constantly exposed to various physical and chemical factors. The interaction of bacteria with epithelial cells in the intestine is largely dependent on mucus, which is mainly composed of highly glycosylated mucin-2, secreted by the goblet cells of the mucosal epithelium. Goblet cells are located along the entire length of the small and large intestine and are responsible for the development and maintenance of the protective layer of mucus through the synthesis and secretion of high-molecular glycoproteins known as mucins. Today, the main task of biological experiments is to study the fundamental mechanisms of the body's adaptation to the effects of physical and chemical factors at the cellular, tissue, and organ levels. In this case, the gastrointestinal tract is the first to respond to exogenous influences of various genesis [7].

Intestinal epithelial cells, along with food, are in constant contact with many foreign antigens that enter biological barriers, the main function of which is to maintain the body's homeostasis. The epithelial integrity necessary for this is ensured by intensive processes of cell regeneration. Among the cells of the intestinal epithelium, a separate group of cells is distinguished - goblet cells (GC), which belong to the so-called mucus-secreting glands. Their name corresponds to the shape of the cells determined during histological studies. The apex of the GC has an expanded, secretory, C-shaped rim of the cytoplasm, called theca, and a narrow base descending to the basal lamina. They produce mucin to lubricate the intestinal contents and protect the epithelium [8]. Mucin type II, which is secreted by the intestinal mucosa and colon, is abundant in the mucosa of the small and large intestine (MUC2, mucin-2). Intestinal epithelial cells also express transmembrane mucins (MUC 1, MUC 3, MUC 4, MUC 12, MUC 13, and MUC 17), which adhere to the apical surface and, together with glycolipids, form a glycocalyx. Mast cells are found in the middle zone of the crypts and are the source of most of the cell types in the intestinal epithelium. The nucleus of the mast cell is located at the base of the long axis and has an apical zone with numerous membrane-bound mucin granules. Their apical surface bears several short microvilli, and in the supranuclear region is the Golgi apparatus with a basally localized rough endoplasmic reticulum. Their secretion plays an important role in chemical and mechanical protection and lubrication of the intestinal wall, as well as in its immune defense, since together with the above, IgA class antibodies are secreted. The GH absorbs IgA, which is initially secreted by B lymphocytes present in the lamina propria, by endocytosis, at its base and sides, and this provides the main source of pro-

tection against microbial organisms in the intestinal lumen [9]. The GH appears as a foreign body located intermittently between the columnar cells of the intestinal epithelium. Their number increases in the direction of the distal part of the small intestine. The contribution of JH among epithelial cells increases caudally from the duodenum (4%) to the distal colon (16%), as does the increase in the number of microbial organisms present from the proximal region of the intestine to the colon [10].

The epithelium of the small intestine is of endodermal origin. These endodermal cells differentiate into different types of secretory and absorptive cells. The remaining layers are derivatives of the splanchnic mesoderm. The endodermal epithelium of the intestine proliferates in the 6th week and completely covers the intestinal opening. Hair appears in the proximal area of the duodenum and small intestine in the 7th week. Hair development reaches the distal area of the small intestine in the 9th week and the distal area of the intestine between the ribs and the abdomen in the 11th week [11].

Simple crypts appear between 10 and 12 weeks. Epithelial cells differentiate and form enterocytes at about 9 weeks. The GI is present in small numbers at 8 weeks. Enteroendocrine cells appear between 9 and 11 weeks, and Paneth cells differentiate from the crypts at about 11 and 12 weeks. Studies have shown that the GI begins to appear by the 9th week of development. The GI is fully formed by 12 weeks of gestation. The temporal and spatial distribution of JH-producing mucins and the evaluation of intestinal alkaline phosphatase (IF) expression during the development of the small intestine of rats showed that glycoprotein development begins at about day 17 of prenatal ontogeny in intestinal epithelial cells, but no morphological signs of the presence of JH were observed. On the 18th day of prenatal ontogeny, the hair epithelium differentiates, and from then on, the first JHs are detected. On the 10th day of postnatal ontogenesis, hairs and crypts were detected in the small intestine, and JH was observed in the apical areas of hairs and crypts [12].

On the 3rd, 10th, 17th, and 25th days after birth, the number of JH increased and regional differences began to be noticed in different sections of the small intestine. IF was not detected in prenatal ontogeny, but by the 3rd week after birth it was weakly expressed in hair cells along its entire length. During the embryogenesis of the small intestine, changes in the temporal and spatial distribution of the GH and the activity of IF occur, which may be associated with changes in the type of nutrition at different stages of postembryonic development. The intestine plays an important role in the digestion and absorption of ingested food, as well as in the excretion of undigested food, microorganisms and their waste products. The functional integrity of epithelial cells in the intestinal mucosa depends on the directed control of the mucosa, the close contacts of intercellular, epithelial cells and the innate and adaptive immune response in the individual. The JH-secreting epithelial lining provides conditions for the excretion of intestinal contents and provides the first line of sperm against the destructive effects of physical and chemical factors induced by ingested food, microbes, and microbial toxins. Microbes and microbial toxins are recognized by intestinal epithelial cells and a sensor system of immune cells, which activate the innate defense system in the intestinal tract. The epithelium of the intestinal mucosa consists of four main types of cells - absorptive enterocytes, JH, Paneth cells and enteroendocrine cells, which are continuously renewed [13]. The morphology of JH is characterized by an elongated theca with mucin granules located below the apical membrane.

In most intestinal infections, JH induction, mucin synthesis, and secretion often occur during the acute phase. However, chronic infection leads to a weakening of the intestinal mucosa and quantitative and qualitative changes in the mucosa, which are caused by changes in the synthesis and secretion of mucins, as well as microbial glycosidases and proteases [14]. Since the intestine is constantly exposed to various biotic and abiotic negative factors, which ultimately lead to hypoxia, in addition to destructive changes, adaptive changes, including changes in cell communication, must occur in it, which are necessary to maintain such functioning. The mucosal and muscular layers and the submucosa develop edema, and coarse hairy connective tissue grows, disrupting the morphofunctional integrity of the "crypt-hair" system. As a result of internal and external changes, the regenerative potential and the strength of the intestinal barrier decrease [15]. The intestinal mucosa, which is mainly based on the secretion of mucin-2, forms a protective line. Although all GHs perform a secretory role, there is evidence that cells in different parts of the intestine respond to various influences and actively participate in maintaining intestinal homeostasis. In this case, changes in the composition of the normal microflora can lead to changes in the homeostatic state and negative consequences for the body. The function of the GI tract is to synthesize and secrete mucus, which serves as a pre-epithelial protective layer at the intestinal barrier and prevents direct contact of antigens, toxins, and bacteria with epithelial cells. The mucosa is composed mostly of highly glycosylated mucin, and its amino acid composition is dominated by the amino acids serine, threonine, and polyene, which are linked by glycosylation to polysaccharides composed of hexoses and hexosamines [16].

The GI tract is continuously renewed every 3–7 days by stem cells at the base of the crypts. Stem cells are the basis of all epithelial cells, including enterocytes and the GI tract. There is a functional differentiation

of enterocytes from the proximal to the distal part of the intestine, which is reflected in the expression specific to this area of the intestine [17]. Destructive changes in the gastroduodenal protective barrier, i.e., the mucous barrier, which includes a layer of mucus and bicarbonates, surface epithelial cells, and secretory epithelial glands, play a major role in the etiology and pathogenesis of ulcer disease. Under the influence of physical and chemical factors, unspecialized changes occur in mast cells, indicating the involvement of this group of cells in the compensatory-adaptive capabilities of the body [18].

The development of the small intestine and its sections, the interaction of its layers, the development of its vessels, the innervation apparatus, topography, histogenesis, and the study of morpho-biochemical changes in this organ are one of the most pressing problems of morphology today and sufficiently justify the need for scientific research in this area.

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